

5.20 A holistic framework to protect Ground Segments of Space Systems against cyber, physical and natural complex threats

7SHIELD: A holistic framework to protect Ground Segments of Space Systems against cyber, physical and natural complex threats by Gerasimos Antzoulatos, Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas – CERTH

7SHIELD project is a collaborative Innovation Action H2020 project aiming to develop a holistic framework to protect EU Ground Segments of Space Systems (GSSS) facilities against cyber and physical threats. Specifically, in the new security landscape of Europe, the GSSS appear as potential “new targets” for “new threats”, especially the combined cyber-physical (C/P) ones. A C/P attack on their installations or communication networks, respectively, would cause cascading impacts and affect the public safety and security of European citizens on one hand and other European Critical Infrastructures (CIs) on the other hand. Hence, the main objective of the 7SHIELD project is to encapsulate mature solutions that are enabled to confront complex threats by covering all the macro stages of crisis management, namely Pre-crisis, Crisis and Post-crises phases, in order to protect GSSS infrastructures and strengthen their resilience.

To achieve this objective, a series of innovation objectives (IO) have been consolidated (Figure 38) including:

- **IO1 – Prevention technologies for physical and cyber threats:** the deployed technologies contribute to the pre-crisis phase by involving the vulnerability assessments of the GSSS assets, secure authentication mechanisms for data access and cascade effects analysis from combined cyber-physical attacks, as well as threat intelligence on cyber-physical threats to enhance the current situational picture with new insights.
- **IO2 – Detection technologies for physical and cyber threats:** state-of-the-art detections technologies have been encompassed to seamlessly and accurately identify potential physical or/and cyber threats to Space Systems, Ground Segments and Satellite data assets.
- **IO3 – Response technologies:** innovative technologies to monitor the evolution of C/P attacks, to strengthen responsiveness and social awareness have been tailored.
- **IO4 – Mitigation technologies for physical and cyber threats:** the appropriate actions to mitigate the consequences of C/P attacks, focusing on the services continuity have been consolidated.

The 7SHIELD Logic Architecture (Figure 39) is a multi-layered architecture in which all the modules and technologies for Pre-crisis, Crisis and Post-crisis phases are integrated into a highly modular, flexible and easily customised framework which integrates twenty (20) Key Results (technology bricks). Seventeen (17) of them are related to prevention (4), detection (7) and response and mitigation (6) technologies. The rest of them concerns the data models, the system integration and the User Interfaces.

The **Cyber-Physical Layer** contains all the data sources that provide to the 7SHIELD platform raw data which are captured from cyber and physical sensors located in the field. *Information sources*, such as drones, CCTVs, thermal and near-infrared sensors, laser fences, etc. from physical world and spam, logs, antivirus, etc. from cyber part will be used to collect data in terms of physical and cyber threats and attacks to the GSSS assets.

Figure 38 - 7SHIELD objectives

The **Detection Layer** encompasses innovative detection tools that enable the identification of abnormal events, cyber and physical threats, and raise alerts. These tools concern the *Data collection from UAVs and edge processing* to detect objects and persons, the *Video surveillance technologies* to detect and recognize faces of suspicious individuals, identify and track objects of interests via processing video streams from surveillance cameras, the *MultiModal Automated Surveillance (MMAS)* system to detect the presence of intruders, such as moving objects and people, within the boundaries of an area under surveillance using thermal and near-infrared sensors coupled with computer vision algorithms, the *Laser-based detection system* detects ground based and aerial intrusion using LIDAR technology. Furthermore, the *Cyber-Attack Detection Framework* is based on the collection of information at several architectural levels (namely: Physical, Network, Operating System, Data Base, Application, and Business Process). The so obtained information will be processed by employing sophisticated data analysis techniques for cyber-attack detection.

Figure 39 - 7SHIELD high level architecture

The **Situational Picture Layer** contains modules to process (validate and correlate) and analyse the real time cyber and physical events in order to identify potential complex cyber and physical attacks. At this level, the obtained information assists operators to comprehend the current *situational picture* which is homogenised and enriched semantically by the 7SHIELD Knowledge Base and Data Models. After that, the updated situational picture proceeds to the Service Layer.

In general, the **Service Layer** contains all the services used by the experts to prevent, manage and mitigate the threats associated with cyber-physical attacks in the Satellite Ground Segment domain. Hence, it encompasses technologies for the *prevention and preparedness activities (pre-crisis phase)* to assess the risk of natural, physical and cyber threats, to model complex CIs and analyse the cascading effects caused by threats into their assets. Furthermore, services for the analysis of social network to support the evaluation of the likelihood of cyber threats are included. A Secure Authentication Mechanism has been adopted to assure that the authentication to these services is performed in a secure way. It facilitates the smooth and secure authentication of users and services to the 7SHIELD framework in a privacy-preserving manner. Other services concern the real-time assessments of the severity level of the ongoing C/P attacks to enrich further the current situational picture, the *First Responders Support System (FRSS)* to enhance field operations and mission coordination of the First Responders (FRs). It enables FR teams to be self-aware and have more information to support effective decision making in the field.

To empower the *responsiveness and social awareness*, a set of innovative technologies will be tailored into the 7SHIELD framework aiming to tackle effectively C/P attacks including the tools to identify and analyse social media posts and create template of emergency messages for engaging citizens and other stakeholders, as well as neutralisation methods of the intruding UAVs. Besides pre-crisis and crisis services, in this layer there are also *post-crisis services* that provide a concrete support to the appropriate actions to mitigate the consequences of physical and cyber-attacks. The *Emergency*

Response Plans from C/P attacks and service/business continuity scenarios for each pilot site are capable to analyse GSSS peculiarities and potential exposures to C/P attacks.

The above technologies and tools will be integrated in a harmonized way in the *7SHIELD Command Control and Coordination System (C3)* which provides an advanced Physical Security Information Management System and Interactive User Interfaces especially suited to support operators of the Ground Segments of Space Systems.

The 7SHIELD project has been planned to be evaluated by five use case pilots (PUCs) as shown in Figure 40, and are as follows:

- PUC1 - Physical Attack in Arctic Space Centre in Sodankylä, Finland
- PUC2 - Cyber-physical attack in Deimos Ground Segment in Spain
- PUC3 - Cyber-physical attack in the ground segment of NOA, Athens
- PUC4 - Threat detection and mitigation on the ICE Cubes Service
- PUC5 – Cyber-attack on the ONDA DIAS platform

Figure 40 - Pilot Use Cases of the 7SHIELD project

So far, the four operational tests in ONDA-DIAS (Italy), in ICE Cubes Services (Belgium), in NOA (Greece) and DEIMOS (Spain) Ground Segments were carried out. During these evaluation cycles, the 7SHIELD tools were gradually integrated and tested over different scenarios and countries aiming to identify gaps or issues that should be improved for the next releases of the system. After the release of the final 7SHIELD framework, three (3) demonstration scenarios will be realised in NOA, FMI and SPACEAPPs premises.